

"PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTINUITY AND CONSISTENCY IN SHAPING INDEPENDENT CRITICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS"

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Abstract: In this article, the development of independent creative thinking is focused on the most important aspects of the student's search, individual thinking activity in the educational process. The issue is aimed at increasing students' interest in the learning process, ensuring their independence and activity, and developing their critical thinking.

Key words: Concept, need, creative, thinking, development, mind, intelligence, concept, heuristic, character, perceptive, level, modeling, logical.

It is of great importance to establish an educational and cognitive process aimed at increasing students' interest in the learning process, ensuring their independence and activity, and developing their critical thinking. In this regard, achieving students' knowledge, supporting their ability to conduct independent observation, is primarily the responsibility of teachers.[1.15]

It is known that in existing scientific literature, the concepts of a student's knowledge and their skills for independent observation are often used together with terms such as "mind," "intelligence," and "thirst for knowledge." Both from pedagogical and psychological perspectives, there are certain differences between these concepts. The great thinker Alisher Navoi emphasized that the concept of "mind" is broader than "knowledge" and identified a number of levels and qualities within it. Some of these qualities are also related to knowledge. The development of independent creative thinking encourages students to engage in research during the learning process. In this context, the most important aspects of an individual's thinking activity become evident. In such conditions, students actively search for solutions and attempt to find heuristic solutions. [2.78]

When developing critical thinking skills in students, it is necessary to take their psychological state into account. In this regard, the methods of J.J.Piaget's "Diagnosis of Children's Intellectual Development," L.S.Rubinstein's "Determining the Level of Acquisition of Modeled Perceptual Actions," M.E. Bershanskiy's "Diagnosis of Imagery-Visual Thinking Actions," and E. Ghaziev's "Development of Logical Thinking Actions" are of significant importance.

As students develop psychological processes such as voluntary attention, memory, perception, thinking, speech, emotional will, etc., the teacher must have great skill in creating a healthy pedagogical environment around them. Teachers should strive to satisfy children's curiosity and, on this basis, develop their motivational areas toward academic subjects. [3.585]

In studying the level of critical thinking in students, it is of great importance to observe their communication processes. The observation method is widely used when comparing students' thinking and communication skills. When developing critical thinking in students, it

is essential for teachers to constantly consider the pedagogical and psychological continuity and coherence.

Problem-based teaching methods also yield effective results in shaping critical thinking in students, as the problem-solving approach in education is reflected in curricula, teacher knowledge presentation, and students' independent work.

Creating problem situations in students' thinking activities fosters qualities such as curiosity, sharp intelligence, independence, interest in learning, and striving for creativity. Problem-based teaching methods also produce effective results in shaping critical thinking, as the problem-based approach is reflected in educational programs, the presentation of teacher knowledge, and students' independent work. [4.764]

Using widely spread innovative methods in pedagogy is advisable to develop critical thinking in students. One of these methods is the "Brainstorming" method ("Mind storming"), through which we can identify the indicators of critical thinking developed in students:

Brainstorming is a method of idea generation. College students, working in small groups, attempt to solve a difficult problem by presenting their personal ideas (generating ideas). It encourages participants to use their imagination and viewpoints. [5.229]

The goal of "Mind Storming" is to create new ideas through the help of small groups. This method encourages students solving problems to think more independently and even generate creative ideas, with all ideas and thoughts expressed being taken into account. Opportunities are provided to expand and enhance the expressed ideas. This approach fulfills all didactic functions, but its main task is to encourage independent understanding and solving of the problem, as well as to awaken the motivation of the learners.

The development of a person's intellectual potential not only involves studying and mastering the fundamentals of the subjects, but also mastering intellectual activity methods that align with educational goals. Intellectual activity involves not only mastering the fundamentals of subjects, but also comparing, analyzing, synthesizing, conceptualizing, generalizing, and applying knowledge in various situations.

Thus, effective methods of activity are generalized, and a common approach for implementing different types of activities is formed using various methods. The depth and strength of students' knowledge are determined not only by its volume but also by its consistency. [6.343]

For the development of students' intellect, it is important to take into account the specific characteristics of intellectual activity when processing information. Intellectual activity consists of processes such as knowledge, memory, the generation and expression of new ideas, and evaluation. Knowledge and intellectual activity types are crucial factors in students' learning. In the educational practice of our country's institutions, intellectual development of an individual and the individualization of learning are of great importance. All of these factors play a significant role in the holistic development of a person.

However, at this stage, shaping creativity in individuals requires a new attitude and a new approach. Traditional education has not provided such great opportunities for the development of students' creative abilities. The key condition for developing creative abilities is giving educational activities a creative character and making them more active. To achieve this, it is necessary to direct students not to passively receive "ready-made" knowledge, but to engage in cooperation and activate their activities, limiting the passive nature of students' activities. [7.53]

This means that the activity in the learning process is a necessary condition for developing students' intellect. In education, activity refers to the person's striving for acquiring knowledge, enhancing attention to intellectual cognition, and showing will, which manifests in the following states of activity:

- Intensive development of the student's perception, attention, memory, and thinking during creative activity.
- Knowing and adhering to moral norms, distinguishing moral concepts (good and evil, alertness and envy, bravery and cowardice).
- Self-awareness and understanding the essence of life's problems.
- Self-development, understanding their shortcomings, and the ability to correct them

Thus, when fostering qualities such as the ability to make independent decisions, having a personal stance, and holding an unwavering idea, it is essential to consider the pedagogical-psychological continuity in the process of developing critical thinking in students. [8.31]

References:

1. Bulanova-Toporkova M.V., Dukhavneva A.V., et al. Pedagogical Technologies: A Textbook for Students of Pedagogical Specialties. - Rostov-on-Don, "Mart", 2002.
2. Zagyzvazinsky V.I. Theory of Education: A Modern Interpretation. // Higher Education. - 2001.
3. Yakubova B.B. A modern method of independent teaching the role of the distance education system information/ Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities ISSN 2749-0866 Vol.1 Issue 1.5 Pedagogical sciences 584-589.
4. Yakubova B.B. Independent Work of Students Through the Internet Pedagogical Conditions of Organization/ Web Of Scientist: International scientific research journal ISSN:2776-0979 (VOLUME 2,ISSUE 5, MAY 2021) 763-766.
5. R.Ishmukhamedov, M.Yuldashev. Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in Education and Upbringing: A Training Manual for Education System Employees, Methodologists, Teachers, Educators, and Trainers. - Tashkent, 2013.
6. K.Turgunboev, M.Ortikova. Foundations of Pedagogical Innovation. - Andijan: "Andijan Publishing and Printing," 2011
7. Vvedensky V.N. Modeling the Professional Competence of a Teacher. / V. N. Vvedensky // Pedagogy. - 2003. - No. 10. - pp. 51-55.
8. Dvoretzkaya A.V. Main Types of Computer-Aided Teaching Tools. / School Technologies. - 2004. - Issue 3. - p. 35.